

**Synthesis and Anti-inflammatory Activity of
some 2-Substituted-phenylethyl-[1,2,4]-triazolo[2,3-*b*]benzo[*e*]-5,6-dihydrobenzothiazoles**

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*Manuscript received 29 January 1991, revised 9 July 1991,
accepted 17 July 1991*

CONDENSED triazoles have been reported to exhibit a variety of pharmacological activities¹. In an attempt to prepare non-acidic non-steroidal anti-inflammatory agents, various 2-substituted-phenylethyl-[1,2,4]-triazolo[2,3-*b*]benzo[*e*]-5,6-dihydrobenzothiazoles (**5a-i**) have been synthesised (Scheme 1) and tested for their anti-inflammatory activity.

α-Tetralone (**1**) was condensed with thiourea and iodine by Dodson-King method² and the resulting 2-aminobenzo[*e*]-4,5-dihydrobenzothiazole (**2**) was then treated with different substituted benzene propanoyl chlorides to get the corresponding amides (**3a-i**). Treatment of **3a-i** with PCl₃ followed by azidolysis with sodium azide in aqueous acetone gave 1-[benzo[*e*]-4,5-dihydrobenzothiazol-2-yl]-5-[2-(substituted-phenyl)ethyl]tetrazoles (**4a-i**). Pyrolysis³ of **4a-i** in tetralin yielded exclusively 2-substituted-phenylethyl-1,2,4-triazolo[2,3-*b*]benzo[*e*]-5,6-dihydrobenzothiazoles (**5a-i**). These were isolated as crystalline solids and characterised by elemental analysis, ir and ¹H nmr spectral data.

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- 3-5a; R=R¹=R²=H
 b; R=R²=H, R¹=OMe
 c; R=R²=H, R¹=OEt
 d; R=R¹=OMe, R²=H
 e; R=R¹=OEt, R²=H
 f; R=R¹=OMe, R²=Et
 g; R=R¹=OEt, R²=Et
 h; R=R¹=OMe, R²=Pr
 i; R=R¹=OEt, R²=Pr

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) H₂NCSNH₂/I₂, (ii) [C₆H₄(R)-
 (R¹)(R²)-CH₂CH₂COCl], (iii) PCl₅, NaN₃/
 aqueous acetone, (iv) Δ.

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. ¹H nmr were recorded using TMS as internal standard.

2-Aminobenzo[e]-4,5-dihydrobenzothiazole (2): A mixture of α-tetralone (1; 1.46 ml, 0.1 mol), thiourea (1.5 g, 0.2 mol) and iodine (2.5 g, 0.1 mol) was heated on a steam-bath for 4 h. The resulting hydroiodide was dissolved in hot water, filtered while hot and the clear solution was neutralised with a strong solution of ammonia. The precipitated solid was washed with water and recrystallised from benzene, (65%, 1.40 g), m.p. 138° (lit.⁴ 140–41°).

2-[3-(Phenyl)propanoyl]aminobenzo[e]-4,5-dihydrobenzothiazole (3): Benzene propanoyl chloride (prepared from the corresponding acid and thionyl chloride) in dry benzene was treated with 2 (0.88 g, 0.1 mol) with shaking. The resulting mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 0.5 h and the crude solid that separated out on dilution was recrystallised

from ethanol to yield 3a (76%, 1.83 g), m.p. 220°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 320 (NH), 1 675 (C=O) and 1 540 cm⁻¹ (NH bend); 3b (74%), 206°; 3c (82%), 215°; 3d (82%), 268°; 3e (86%), 284°; 3f (80%), 221°; 3g (85%), 209°; 3h (77%), 235°; 3i (83%), 257°.

1-[Benzo[e]-4,5-dihydrobenzothiazol-2-yl]-5-[2-phenylethyl]tetrazole (4): A mixture of 3a (0.844 g, 0.004 mol) and PCl₅ (0.883 g, 0.004 mol) was heated at 100° for 1 h until evolution of HCl fumes ceased. Excess POCl₃ was then removed under reduced pressure and the imidoyl chloride was treated with an ice-cold solution of sodium azide (0.487 g, 0.075 mol) and excess of sodium acetate in water (25 ml) and acetone (30 ml) with stirring. Stirring was continued overnight, acetone removed under reduced pressure, remaining aqueous portion extracted with CHCl₃, and the dried CHCl₃ extract was then concentrated to a gummy material which was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether to give 4a (60%, 0.506 g), m.p. 201°; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 672 (C=N), 1 429 (N=N), 1 309 (C-N), 1 270 (N-N=N), 1 095 and 1 030 cm⁻¹ (tetrazole ring); 4b (60.4%), 179°; 4c (62%), 183°; 4d (58%), 219°; 4e (66%), 227°; 4f (61%), 181°; 4g (59%), 199°; 4h (64%), 191°; 4i (62%), 187°.

2-[2-(Phenyl)ethyl]-[1,2,4-triazolo[2,3-b]benzo[e]-5,6-dihydrobenzothiazole (5): A solution of 4a (0.1 mol) in tetralin was refluxed for 1 h, then tetralin removed under pressure, the residue extracted with CHCl₃, organic extract concentrated and the residual mass subjected to column chromatography. Elution with benzene-ethyl acetate (1:1) afforded 5a as white crystals (40%, 0.202 g), m.p. 205°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 020 (CH), 1 626 (C=N), 1 535 (C=C), 1 330 (C-N), 1 215 (C-O-C asymmetric), 1 097 (triazole ring) and 670 cm⁻¹ (C-S); δ (CDCl₃) 2.3–2.6 (6H, m, 5-CH₂-, 6-CH₂- and ArCH₂CH₂C=N-), 3.41 (2H, t, ArCH₂CH₂C=N-), 7.0–8.28 (9H, m, ArH); 5b (42%), 170–72°; 5c (40%), 183°; 5d (45%), 178°; 5e (43%), 185–86°; 5f (42%), 196°; 5g (40%), 189°; 5h (44%), 200°; 5i (42%), 212°. All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Anti-inflammatory activity: The compounds were assessed for anti-inflammatory activity at 100 mg/kg oral dose by acute carrageenan-induced oedema in rat paw following the reported technique⁶. The experiments were performed on male Charles Foster albino rats (120–150 g) in groups of five each and the paw volume was measured with a 7107 UGO Basil volume differential meter, 2 and 3.5 h after carrageenan injection. The results indicate that anti-inflammatory activity is unaffected by the substitution at 1-position of the tetrazole ring. However, condensation of benzo[e]-4,5-dihydrobenzothiazole with a 1,2,4-triazole moiety containing an unsubstituted phenylethyl group results in loss of activity but substitution on the phenyl ring of phenylethyl group has a significant effect on anti-inflammatory activity. 1,3-Diethoxy substitution on the phenyl ring imparted maximum activity of 53.94%. Phenyl butazone

was used as the reference standard in all of the screening tests.

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